
The New Proposed Energy Subsidy Reform in Egypt

Impact and Recommendations for
Implementation

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Impact and Recommendations of the New Subsidy Program

Effective Communication and Mitigation Schemes Needed for Implementation

Why We Did This Study

In this policy paper, we analyze the new proposed energy subsidy cuts program in Egypt and suggest recommendations to mitigate its negative effects. The paper is very important as it studies the impact of the proposed program with reference to real data obtained from previous studies and statistics of Egypt's energy sector.

To achieve these, we evaluated (1) potential direct impact on individuals and households and (2) indirect impact on consumer good services, quality of life, employment and income levels. During this review, we analyzed literature on the topic along with referring to countries like Brazil, Yemen and Iran for their experience in implementing subsidy cuts.

What Do We Recommend?

The results of the study recommend actions to address a mitigation scheme with careful implementation sequence and more effective communication mechanism of the subsidy cuts process, along with applying a targeted cash transfer program that ensures that the proposed reforms benefit the underserved and would have fair eligibility criteria to receiving subsidies.

What We Found?

Subsidy reforms to LPG, kerosene will have the highest direct impact on low-income households. Adjusting to domestic prices will increase the incidence of poverty by 4.4% according to the World Bank. Removing subsidies from natural gas and gasoline will have a minimal impact on low-income households.

Price increases to natural gas will have the highest indirect impact on household incomes, every 10% increase in natural gas prices will cause a 6.9% increase in electricity prices. Food prices are expected to increase, as the industry is energy-intensive and relies heavily on transportation of goods. Further studies needed to obtain an estimate of the impact. Housing prices are also expected to rise, as construction materials production is energy-intensive, such as cement, which will experience a 4.5% increase in production cost if subsidies are removed.

Kerosene and diesel shortages and black markets are expected to be an issue, particularly in rural areas. This will impact the productivity of cross-country transportation and the availability of goods in rural areas. Rotating blackouts are expected to impact low- and middle-income households more than higher-income ones, particularly those in informal settlements.

Farmers will be impacted with a 4% increase in fertilizers manufacturing cost, increased diesel prices, and potential shortages. This will directly impact operational costs, productivity, and thus their income. Workers in the manufacturing industry will be vulnerable to operational downsizing due to increase production costs, as well as possible decrease in foreign direct investment due to reduction of energy subsidies.

IMPACT

From this, we took our research further to studying the direct and the indirect impacts of the new proposed subsidy cuts on Egyptians. The report will study the direct impact of subsidy cuts on household costs, the prices of LPG, Kerosene and Diesel, electricity, natural gas and gasoline. As for the indirect impact the study will look into the impact on consumer goods and services, quality of life and employment and income levels.

ON HOUSEHOLD COSTS

Energy Subsidy reforms will affect household costs for low-income households significantly more than it will affect middle and high-income households. Because of their low consumption of energy, low-income households cannot further reduce their consumption in response to price hikes, thus it consumes a larger income share (UNDP, 2012). Studies conducted in developing Asian countries that experienced subsidy cuts in electricity and petrol found that low-income households spent 171% more of their income on cooking fuels, 120% more on transportation, and 67% more on electricity in comparison with middle- and high-income households (Goldthau, Sovacool, 2011). Comparable patterns can be expected in Egypt.

Studies conducted in several developing countries (Granado et al, 2012) show that on average a fuel price increase of \$0.25 per liter will decrease a household's real income by 7.4% in Middle East¹ countries, accounting for 3.6% direct (purchasing fuel) and 4.2% in indirect (increase in goods and transportation costs) impacts. The study shows that real income of the lowest income households are impacted by 8.6% (4% direct and 4.6% indirect), and that most of the direct impact is from the subsidy cuts of LPG (1.46%) and kerosene (1.18%).

DIRECT IMPACT (ENERGY COST)

LPG, Kerosene and Diesel

According to World Bank estimation, removing subsidies from LPG, diesel and kerosene will increase the incidence of poverty by 4.4% (World Bank, 2005). LPG and kerosene account for the majority of households' energy consumption, 47% and 40% respectively (Suding,

¹Middle Eastern countries in the study were Jordan and Lebanon.

2010), and 95% of LPG produced is used for household consumption (Khattab, 2007). Figure 4 shows the structure of energy consumption in Egypt (Suding, 2010).

As these energy sources are heavily subsidized and are used as main energy sources in rural areas, phasing out kerosene, diesel and LPG subsidies will have a significant impact on rural households (Abouleinein, 2009). Subsidies for these sources of energy increase the purchasing power of lower income families and improve their living conditions as it LPG is used as an affordable cooking fuel, kerosene for electricity for households in rural areas and informal settlements, and diesel in agriculture equipment and transportation.

source: Suding, 2010

Figure 1: Structure of energy consumption in Egypt

Electricity

Electricity Prices are expected to increase 6.9% for every 10% increase in natural gas prices, according to a study by the Egyptian Center for Economic Studies, ECES (Abouleinein et al, 2009). This is due to the fact that electricity generation is highly dependent on natural gas, with over 60% of natural gas consumed by power plants (Khattab, 2007).

Natural Gas and Gasoline

Gasoline and natural gas subsidy removal will decrease low-income individuals' income by a monthly rate of LE 0.14 and 0.36 per capita respectively (World Bank, 2005). This minimal impact on low-income households is because the main beneficiaries of these subsidies are high- and middle-income households that are connected to the natural gas network and can afford cars. Only 14% of Cairo households own a car (Elshahed, 2013) and less nationwide

and only 10% of the urban poor benefit from the natural gas network because of the high installment cost.

INDIRECT IMPACT

Consumer Goods and Services

Removing energy subsidies will have a negative impact on the Egyptian economy, which will surely affect the social justice and welfare of individuals. Removing subsidies will increase the energy bill of all firms and decrease their profitability, which will later increase the prices of all services and goods, which will also affect negatively the social welfare of individuals. The highly affected sectors from subsidy removal are those who rely heavily on petroleum products such as cement, fertilizers, electricity, paper, glass, iron and steel. Also energy subsidy removal will lead to a higher increase in the prices of transportation for both passengers and goods (Khattab, 2007). According to the ECES study mentioned earlier, removing energy subsidies will result in an increase in the cost of electricity, transportation and communication, which will raise the CPI by almost 60% and 43% respectively (Abouleinein et al, 2009).

For every 10% increase in natural gas prices, the Consumer Price Index² (CPI) will increase by 0.5%. Electricity has the highest direct impact on household finances (compared to other sources of energy), with 2.3% of household income spent on electricity, which is dependent on natural gas (Abouleinein et al, 2009). On the other hand, gasoline has the lowest effect on the CPI, as it has the lowest consumption among all the fuel types (Ibid).

The consumer price level for the poorest urban households will increase 10% if fuel market prices are only imposed on energy-intensive industries, this will reduce subsidies by 27%. On the other hand, expanding subsidy cuts to households and other activities will cause a 34% increase in the consumer price level, and reduce subsidies by 75%(Abouleinein et al, 2009). For rural households with the lowest income, it will increase by 11% and 37% respectively (Ibid).Figure 1 (Ibid) below shows the percentage increase in price index in the case of removing all subsidies from different industries and the CPI at the national level.

² Consumer Price Index (CPI) measures changes in the price level of a market basket of consumer goods and services purchased by households. It is used as a measure of the average change over time in the prices paid by consumers.

source: (Abouleinein et al, 2009)

Figure 1: Percentage increase in Price Index if all subsidies are removed

The food industry is energy-intensive, consuming 83% of fuel oil (Abouleinein et al, 2009). Removing subsidies from petroleum products used in energy-intensive industries will indirectly cause a hike in food prices. This will impact low-income households more as the share of income spent on food is more than higher-income households (Ibid).

Changes to the price of diesel will affect the transportation industry twice as much as changing the price of gasoline would (Abouleinein et al, 2009). Construction costs, and subsequently real estate and housing prices will increase as a result of removing subsidies from industries. Industries that purchase fuel at market price will experience an increase in manufacturing costs. The highest impact will be an 11% increase in the production cost of the manufacturing of cement, followed by 4.5% increase for basic iron, casting steel by 3.5%, glass and glass products by 3%, and aluminum by 3% (Khattab, 2007). This will negatively impact the purchase power of lower-income individuals, who already find it difficult to purchase housing units.

QUALITY OF LIFE

Access to Energy

Kerosene shortages occur when it is more subsidized than diesel, as kerosene gets substituted for diesel by the transport sector. Black market share is likely to emerge due to this shortage and significantly impact the lower income groups the most, as they are the main beneficiaries of subsidies for these lower quality fuels. This does not negate the fact that there are leakages

to unintended groups (Fattouh, El-Katiri, 2012). The potential of fuel shortages may affect the productivity of cross-country transportation. Distributors and drivers may decide not to transport products and goods to rural areas that are far from urban centers to save fuel. This will affect the availability of goods to the inhabitants of these areas, who are usually low-income households.

Electricity Supply

Rotating blackouts, which are a result of electricity shortages, are expected to affect low- and middle-income households more than higher-income ones. The majority of middle- and low-income households are in informal settlements, which are self-built areas, not planned by the Governorates. Many of these households pay electricity fees irrespective of their use as they do not have electricity meters installed because they are illegally connected to the electricity grid and have been later formalized by the officials by paying a monthly fee to remain connected illicitly (Salah El Din, 2013). One resident of Ezbet El Haggana, one of Cairo's largest informal settlements, accounts that even during prolonged blackouts, his monthly electricity fee remained constant at 200 EGP (Ibid).

The Electricity Ministry is currently facing difficulties securing funds to purchase imported fuel for power generation. This has already caused several electricity shortages in the last eight months. This is expected to exacerbate with fuel price increases with the removal of the energy subsidy and the low foreign reserves available. Electricity generation power units rely primarily on fossil fuels, with only 10% generated from renewable energy sources, such as the Aswan High Dam (AboAlabass, 2013). According to the Electricity Ministry, the electricity power plants consume approximately 90 million cubic meters of natural gas or low-quality diesel fuel (Ibid).

An electricity supply gap of 2,500 MW is expected in the high-consumption summer months, and is forecasted to increase if fuel and foreign currency liquidity shortages persist, according to the head of the Egyptian Electric Utility and Consumption Protection Regulatory Agency (AboAlabass, 2013). Household use is estimated to be the highest consumer of electricity supply at 39%, followed by the industrial sector at 33.5% according to the American Chamber of Commerce in Egypt (Tashima, 2012).

EMPLOYMENT AND INCOME LEVELS

Unemployment rates can increase as an indirect result of energy price increases, particularly for farmers and factory workers. High-labor industries that are also energy-intensive, such as the manufacturing industry may decide to underutilize capacity to lower its costs, particularly in the current transitional period.

Agriculture

Farmers will be negatively impacted by a 4% increase in manufacturing cost of fertilizers (Khattab, 2007), which is likely to be transferred into an increase in consumer prices. This increase in fertilizer costs may force them to cultivate less of their land or grow produce that requires less fertilizer, affecting the food security of the country.

Farmers use lots of machinery in the agricultural process. Increasing the prices of fuel will increase the production and transportation costs of crops. For example in wheat farming, the farmers use diesel to operate machines like: water pumps, tractors and machines that separates the grain from the straw.

The current diesel shortage already had a negative impact on farmers, as it led to the emergence of the black market, from where they get the diesel at higher prices. This effect transferred into higher prices for equipment and machinery rental for farmers. These effects are expected to increase with energy subsidy removal and further subsequent shortages in diesel supply.

This rise in the production and transportation cost will lead to the increase of the prices of crops afterwards, and with the unchanging average income of the average citizens, they will not be able to afford to buy their basic needs from food leading to social injustice.

Manufacturing

The manufacturing sector is energy-intensive using almost 30% of the total petroleum products consumption in Egypt, 26% of the total natural gas consumption in Egypt and 38% of the total electricity consumption in Egypt (Khattab, 2007). This constitutes 20-25% of total energy subsidies. They also benefit indirectly from subsidies given to the transportation sector in the form of lower transportation costs, which use almost 42% of the petroleum products (Ibid). This relationship makes operational costs highly dependent on energy pricing. Table 1 shows the percentage increase in production costs in several industries as a

result of reducing fuel subsidies and the electricity price increases (Khattab, 2007). Operating with market price fuel will have a significant impact on operational costs and may lead to downsizing of operations, leaving low-skilled workers the most vulnerable.

	10%	20%	30%	40%	60%	100%
Manufacture of paper & paper products	0.22%	0.43%	0.65%	0.85%	1.28%	2.15%
Manufacture of chemicals & chemical products	0.15%	0.31%	0.46%	0.60%	0.90%	1.53%
Manufacture of fertilizers & nitrogen compounds	0.41%	0.82%	1.23%	1.62%	2.42%	4.10%
Manufacture of glass & glass products	0.33%	0.66%	0.99%	1.30%	1.94%	3.31%
Manufacture of cement, lime & plaster	1.09%	2.18%	3.28%	4.24%	6.37%	10.92%
Manufacture of articles of concrete, cement & plaster	0.09%	0.18%	0.27%	0.35%	0.52%	0.89%
Manufacture of basic iron & steel	0.45%	0.90%	1.36%	1.78%	2.68%	4.52%
Casting of iron & steel	0.35%	0.70%	1.04%	1.27%	1.91%	3.48%
Manufacture of basic precious & non-ferrous metals (including aluminum)	0.29%	0.58%	0.87%	1.09%	1.64%	2.91%

source: (Khattab, 2007)

Table 1: Percentage increase in total production cost of main energy-intensive industries due to reducing fuel subsidies and the resulting electricity price increases

Investment and Employment

The presence of subsidies is an incentive that attracts many local and foreign investments to operate in Egypt to benefit from the low energy products prices, as it will increase their profit margin. This created many job opportunities for low and medium skilled workers in factories and industries. Removing subsidies will decrease economic growth due to the increase in the production cost. The decrease in the profit margin for investors may lead to either downsizing the size of their investments in Egypt, or to shift it to another country where there are better economic opportunities. These turbulences and slowing down of the economic growth have a direct effect on the unemployment rate, as it is linked to the size of investments and how it attracts investors. This translates into the number of job opportunities these investments are able to introduce in the labor market.

Background

For years, it was obvious that the government has resisted cutting subsidies for fear of igniting inflation and the wrath of citizens. However, the government now is under a renewed pressure to tackle the issue of subsidy for several reasons; amongst them is its aspiration to obtaining a \$3.2 an emergency loan from the International Monetary Fund (IMF). That explains, to some extent, the role that subsidy cuts can play in both averting a balance of payment and securing the preconditions mandated by the IMF for getting the loan.

In Egypt, a typical better-off Egyptian receives roughly twice the amount in subsidies as a genuinely poor one. As the middle classes, the well-off and big businesses are the biggest beneficiaries of the current subsidy system. At the same time, subsidies to fuels and food account for almost one-third of the total government budget, or over 10% of the country's GDP which explains the importance of the subsidy issue and how it is a key to solving most Egypt's public finance problems. The figures below further explain the amounts the government spends on subsidies:

Figure 2: Ratio of domestic price and subsidies to actual price 2007/2008 (Shalaby, 2010)

Items	Amount of Subsidies (in LE billions)	%
Natural gas subsidy	8,963.3	40.6
Biogas subsidy	4,731.4	21.4
Difference of Diesel (solar) prices	6,074.9	27.5
Fuel oil (mazout) price difference	1,108.2	5.0
Gasoline price differences	976.5	4.4
Kerosene price difference	223.8	1.0
Total	22,078.10*	100.00

Source: Ministry of Finance (various issues).

Table 2: Percentage of subsidy to energy products items 2005/6 (Khattab, 2007)

	Price (Average)	Financial Cost	Economic Cost	Subsidy (Financial)	Subsidy (Economic)			
Electricity	LE/MWh	LE/MWh	LE/MWh	LE million	LE million			
Industry	140-250	430-450	530-560	6,300	10,640			
Agriculture	130-150	435-460	555-590	935	1,760			
Commercial	240-300	435-460	555-590	720	1,450			
Residential	157	480-520	575-625	10,350	16,650			
Government	150-250	435-460	555-590	735	1,550			
Other	100-350	440-520	530-625	2,880	4,800			
Total				21,920	36,850			
Natural Gas	LE/CM	LE/CM	LE/CM	LE million	LE million			
Power	0.25	0.45	0.55-0.85	5,860	13,360			
Industry	0.3-0.60	0.45	0.60-0.90	1,150	2,820			
Residential	0.25	0.50	0.65-0.95	754	1,315			
Other	0.25-0.5	0.50	0.65-0.95	2,250	4,880			
Total				10,014	22,375			
Petroleum	LE/ton	LE/ton	LE/ton	LE million	LE million			
LPG	225	1,840	4,350	9,650	19,750			
Gasoline	1,750	2,430	5,280	5,625	16,680			
Kerosene	1320	2,430	5,280	830	1,530			
Gas Oil	1320	2,210	4,920	12,870	26,775			
Fuel Oil	995	1,975	2,980	6,750	16,380			
Total				35,725	81,115			
Memo items								
Fiscal year	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010
GDP (LE billion)	417	485	536	618	730	847	1008	1181
Budget (LE billion)	127	145	161	207	212	241	340	319
Subsidies (LE billion)	21	25	30	69	52	64	133	93
Energy subsidies in 2010 (financial) = 21% of budget = 73% of total subsidies Energy subsidies in 2010 (economic) = 11.9% of GDP								

Table 3: Approximate amounts of energy subsidies in 2009/2010 (Castel, 2012)

With the government spending at least 65% of the actual costs of the different energy prices, the Egyptian Prime Minister Hesham Kandil has announced the intentions of the government of a gradual reform of energy subsidies. The proposal suggested setting a cap on how much subsidized fuel and cooking gas each household can purchase.

Another reason behind the cuts is the unprecedented shortage in foreign currency reserves. In January 2013, the Central Bank of Egypt (CBE) has issued a report on how injections of foreign currency in 2011 and 2012 were allocated. The report indicated that CBE made a total of \$36 billion available for four major spending items during the mentioned two years, including purchases of petroleum and wheat. The report has also shown that the bank allocated about \$13 billion in 2011 only, out of \$21 billion, for providing foreign currency to foreign investors who decided to exit the market in the wake of the Tahrir square uprising in early 2011, besides removing any restrictions on investment outflows in order to cover capital flight (Ahram Online, 2013).

The crisis further worsened after president Morsi's declaration of the new constitution in December 2012 raising more concerns among Egyptians who feared a further devaluation of the pound on the back of further political upheavals. As a result, on December 27th, 2012, the dollar traded at L.E 6.42 to the dollar, a considerable decline when considering that the pound fell from L.E 6.02 in January 2012 to L.E 6.11 at the beginning of December (Tashima, 2013).

Consequently the government has applied for a loan from the IMF and the negotiations began early on after the revolution, yet the agreement is still on hold due to the government's reluctance to pass a number of austerity measures and fiscal adjustments including tax increases and reductions in fuel subsidies needed to secure the loan. The loan stems its significance from its concern that the country receiving the loan is able to restore foreign investment and market confidence, especially after the Egyptian banking downgraded and stock market got plummeted. Wide criticism has been voiced against the government economic policy. It has been viewed to increase the burden on the lower income Egyptian by increasing indirect taxes and reducing subsidies. The proposed reform helps address one of the main problems; were subsidized commodities are available to everyone, regardless of their income or wealth (Rohac, 2013).

The Proposed Subsidy System

Energy

According to Egyptian Oil Minister Osama Kamal; the annual subsidies on petroleum products totaling 120 billion Egyptian pounds (\$17.5billion) in the current fiscal year helps the well-off more than those in need. As a result, the government is proposing a new subsidy system that includes a coupon system (Alarabiya, Apr.8, 2013). He further adds that implementing the new plan will create enemies amongst the wealthy in society for the government enemies.

The new coupon plan will be voted on after a new constitution is approved by the constituent assembly. Prime Minister Hisham Kandil explained that subsidies would be changed to a coupon or smartcard system to ensure that only the poor received cheaper cooking gas, rather than the entirety of the population.

The government program is a cut in energy subsidies, which are estimated to reach 120billion Egyptian pounds (\$17.5billion) in the current fiscal year. Energy prices for energy intensive industries will be gradually raised to reach production costs in three years (Hussien, 2013).However, the fate of other industries is not clear yet.

The government also intends to rationalize subsidized fuel through a system of smart cards allowing drivers a limited amount of fuel. The smart card system will be implemented to sell subsidized petrol on government vehicles in May 2013 and on private cars in July 2013.Under the new system, vehicles with smaller engines (1600 cc or smaller) will be assigned an annual 1800 liters at the subsidized price. If consumption exceeds that amount the riders will be obliged to pay at the market price. Cars with larger engines sizes will not be eligible to receive the subsidy and they will have to pay at the market price.

Cooking Gas

As for the cooking gas, the government has a database of 12 million families, or 65 million individuals that are in need of cooking gas subsidies. Individuals who are not listed in the database will be charged with the world market prices. The Egyptian Prime Minister stated that “we also have a database of families who have natural gas piped into their houses. These

(also) will not get coupons. This will save the state about 80 million butane cylinders, because the state will offer 280 million cylinders compared to the current 360 million.” (Nuqudy Newsletter, 2012) As for the actual price changes, right now most Egyptians pay LE5 per cylinder of butane; outside the coupon system the price will be LE30, while the world price is LE68. (Nuqudy Newsletter, 2012)

Gasoline

The 95 octane gasoline, which is mostly used by the rich for their luxury cars, is currently sold by the state at LE2.75 per liter while the true cost is LE4.85 per liter. On the other and, 80 octane gasolines are widely used by the poor and are sold at a rate of LE0.90 per liter while the free-market cost is LE3.35.

Diesel

Egypt, which used to be a significant gas exporter, is now struggling to cover the cost of energy imports after the 2011 uprising which drove away investors and drained its foreign reserves to a critical level which is insufficient to cover three months of total imports. The country needs around 500 million cubic feet of gas a day to cover its electricity needs and an additional 500-700 million cubic feet for its industrial needs. (Alsherif, 2013)

Recently, Qatar said it would extend gas supplies to Egypt during the summer, when energy consumption reaches a peak, and the two countries were close to an agreement on the detailed terms. Some of these supplies from Qatar could be provided through a government tender for importing liquefied natural gas. The government currently supplies around 42.5 million liters of diesel a day but long lines at gas stations suggest that demand is still not being met. Farmers say they are concerned about a shortage of diesel supply to power irrigation pumps and tractors for the harvest season which may hinder this year's wheat crop.

Case Studies

Over the past two decades, many countries across the world have undertaken intensive reforms to its energy subsidy programs aiming to reduce the associated fiscal burden and rationalize its energy consumption.

Successful models in energy subsidy reforms have been mostly accompanied with carefully designed mitigating measures to protect vulnerable groups from energy-price increases like Brazil and Yemen. Additionally, governments in those countries were able to ease the public resistance to the subsidy cuts through a well-developed communication policy based on transparency and community participation. On the contrary, in some countries like Iran, the government failed to continue its energy subsidy reform process after losing the support of the parliament, which led to freezing its reform program until further notice. (International Monetary Fund (IMF), 2013, p.5)

This chapter presents case studies reviewing energy subsidy reforms in Brazil, Yemen and Iran. All of these countries introduced policies to restructure its subsidy with solid mitigating measures to provide a form of social protection to the underserved.

Brazil

The Brazilian government started its subsidy reform process in 1990 to liberalize Brazil energy sector and open the door for domestic and foreign investment in this sector (International Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD), 2010, p.6). The government's new agenda was strongly opposed by different interest groups including trade unions, consumers, industry and nationalists (IMF, 2010, p.11). At the time, the Brazilian government adopted a gradual approach of phasing out the subsidy in order to build public support for the reforms promising consumers that privatization and liberalization of the energy sector would produce social benefits and improve services.

This gradual approach started by removing the government subsidy on products like asphalt, lubricants, and gasoline for airplanes, which generally benefited politically weak stakeholders, while the politically more difficult subsidies like the liquid fuels used for transportation was removed in the end of the reform process. Additionally, the popularity and credulity of President Fernando Henrique Cardoso (served from 1995 to 2003) was an

essential factor behind the government's success in liberalizing the energy sector and the removal of the subsidy (IMF, 2010, p.11).

Towards the end of 2001, the government was able to increase the prices of all the fuel products. Currently there is no official government price, however, Agencia Nacional do Petroleo, an official governmental body, monitors fuel products prices which includes gasoline, fuel ethanol, diesel, natural gas for vehicles, and liquefied natural gas (IISD, 2010, p.10).

The reform of the subsidy policy in Brazil was accompanied with a number of mitigating measures to provide coverage for the vulnerable groups. On the top of these measures was the continuing of providing fuel subsidy for poor regions like Amazonia for a period of 10 years until 2012 (IMF, 2010, p.10). In addition, the government adopted a social targeted program called conditional cash transfer program, the Bolsa Familia in 2003. This program includes gas-vouchers to compensate low-income households for the increase in LPG prices and a conditional cash transfers program (IMF, 2010, p.8).

Yemen

Over the last 23 years Yemen has implemented different reform programs to reduce energy subsidies in order to save its economy and ensure that the subsidies reach those in need. The size of these subsidies has fluctuated over time, reflecting changes in international fuel prices, consumption volumes, the exchange rate, and domestic prices. Statistics provided by the government showed that 40 percent of fuel subsidies went to the richest before its reforms went into effect (IMF, 2012, p.72).

In 2005 the Yemeni government with the help of IMF and World Bank launched a gradually subsidy removal system increasing the prices of the fuel by 130 percent leading to social unrest nationwide. This decision was revoked in 2006 with a sharp hike in the basic goods prices (United Nations Development Program (UNDP), 2012, p.30).

New reforms were introduced in 2010 including a 30 percent increase in gasoline, diesel, and kerosene prices in a period of nine months. This new reforms accompanied with a government campaign to promote the replacing of diesel-fueled power generators with gas-

fueled ones. Subsidy on diesel provided for all commercial uses was removed (IMF, 2012, p.72).

Another group of reforms implemented during the political uprising against Ali Abdallah Saleh in 2011 where the government increased the price of the gasoline by 66 percent while doubling the prices of the diesel and kerosene (IMF, 2012, p.72). These reforms came after the major oil pipeline had been sabotaged which led to huge increases in the prices of fuel due to the emergence of the black market. Therefore, the public opinion saw the government reforms as the only way to guarantee the stability of supply regardless to the price (IMF, 2012, p.72).

By 2012, the Yemeni's subsidy bill was reduced to 10 percent of GDP comparing to 14 percent of GDP in 2008 (UNDP, 2012, p.72). Yemeni government has tried different mitigation measures while undertaking subsidy reforms. Most of these measures focused on improving the safety nets of vulnerable groups like the following:

The establishing of "Social Welfare Fund" (SWF) in 1996 as domestic agency to fight poverty: the SWF implemented a conditional cash transfers program to ease the impact of the removal of the fuel subsidy. In 2008 the parliament approved a new Social Protection law to expand the benefits provided by the government to households (IMF, 2012, p.74). The cash transfer scheme was expanded in 2010 when the government implemented a 30 percent increase in the fuel prices. Currently, the government is planning to expand conditional social cash transfers program in order to mitigate the effect the 2012 subsidy reforms (IMF, 2012, p.74).

The Public Works Project: the project offered a short-term employment and support for contractors through a labor-intensive public works program. In addition, an initiative was launched by the Social Fund for Development to support the microenterprises through long term loans (IMF, 2012, p.74).

The government also supported some initiatives to rationalize the consumption of the fuel. For example it encouraged the conversion of kerosene to LPG for residential use starting in early 2000's. Also, in 2010 the diesel-fueled electricity plants were converted to natural gas (UNDP, 2012, 30).

Despite that these mitigation measures still limited in reaching the majority of poor people in Yemen who are mostly affected by the removal of the subsidy, it helped the government to reduce the public resistance to the subsidy reforms (IMF, 2012, p.75).

Iran

Following the hypertrophy of the subsidy bill, the Iranian government decided in 2010 to implement a multiphase reform program that included a broad cash transfer program for households (IMF, 2013, p.27). The government decided to increase the domestic prices of the fuel over five years to 90 percent of the international prices. The first phase of the program included an increase of all major fuel products and natural gas. The government also raised the prices of the services like electricity, water and bread (IMF, 2013, p.27).

To create a balance after the substantially increase in the prices, the government started a cash transfer program for millions of households. This program was funded by the revenue that the government collected after increasing the prices of the energy products. In addition to the cash transfer, the government also has allocated part of the revenues to give 7,000 domestic energy production enterprises direct assistance (IMF, 2013, p.27).

At least 80 percent of the price increases of the revenues were allocated by the government to the cash transfer program and 20 percent of the revenues were allocated for the support of 7,000 energy production enterprises. While implementing the cash transfer program the Iranian government faced a tremendous challenge of identifying the groups that will benefit from the cash transfer program. In the end, the government decided that all the citizens could apply to benefit from the cash for the program (IMF, 2013, p.27).

During the implementation of the reforms, the government launched a massive public relations campaign to educate the public about the importance and the details of the programs. The campaigns focused on informing the citizens on how they will benefit from these reforms and they will to register for the cash transfer program (IMF, 2013, p.29).

At the same time, the government introduced new tariffs on electricity, natural gas, and water which forced many household consumers to pay high prices for the use of energy products. The tariffs took into consideration the difference between the regions in terms of living conditions and standard. For example, in regions that enjoyed warmer weather, the consumers paid lower prices for the fuel as there is a high demand for the air conditions,

while in other regions where natural gas was not available, heating costs subsided (IMF, 2013, p.28).

Following a political crisis in 2012 between the government and the opposition over the subsidy reform program, the parliament decided to put the second phase of the reform program on hold. The decision came after the majority of the parliament refused to vote for the government proposed cash transfer program new budget that projected to substitute the cash transfers with more targeted cash transfers for low-income groups (IMF, 2013, p.27).

Conclusion

After the 25th January Revolution and the new wave of hope for a better future, the Egyptian government has been proposing new programs to ensure social justice and equity especially in the subsidies. In the current subsidy system the underserved are getting twice less than those who are well-off and most probably do not need the subsidies. With the ongoing energy production crisis where we can see long queues of cars at gas stations to fill their car and truck tanks, the calls for reforms has grew louder. Therefore the government is looking into implementing a new subsidy cuts program with more focus on reaching those in need.

In our study, we found out that subsidy cuts to LPG, kerosene will cause great negative impact on the lower-income individuals where it is expected that poverty rates will increase at a 4.4%. However cutting subsidies for the natural gas will have very little effect in those who are underserved as they cannot access this service in the first place.

High indirect impacts will results on households' income where every 10% increase in natural gas prices will cause a 6.9% increase in electricity prices. Food prices therefore, are expected to rise where production consumes very large numbers of energy. The domino effect reaches housing prices where they are also expected to rise, as construction materials production is energy-intensive, such as cement, which will experience a 4.5% increase in production cost if subsidies are removed. Black markets will emerge and more power cuts to be experienced. Fertilizers manufacturing costs are expected to rise 4% and therefore causing a continuation of the domino effect reaching food prices and decreasing production.

We therefore looked into previous experiences of other countries who have achieved energy subsidy cuts programs. We used Brazil, Yemen and Iran as reference and for analysis. We found out that creating a mitigation scheme with careful consequences is very important where it helps ensure that the increase of prices would not hit those most in need for the subsidies. We learned then when governments are able to communicate effectively what will happen, why is it important and how this will benefit everyone, that the people were more receptive and cooperative during implementation. Another final learning is that providing a targeted cash program with effective information could also be an option.

Recommendations for Executive Action

From the above study we realize that subsidy cuts are needed and should begin now. However, our recommendations are based on how to best implement the cuts without losing the main essence of the subsidy which is helping out those who are less privileged. We therefore recommend the following:

Create a Mitigation Scheme with a Careful Sequence

This is very important to ensure that the less privileged receive the benefits from the cuts. If the cuts are implemented sudden and without planning phases for testing and development then there will be huge problems affecting people directly and indirectly. As we have seen from the case studies listed above, that cuts came gradually and in phases. The government should plan cuts in the subsidies in each energy source at a time and not all of the cuts implemented in the same time.

Effective Communication of the Process

Again, from the above case studies we see that there is a very important component of the implementation which is communication. In Brazil they have communicated the cuts in a very open and transparent participatory way. In Yemen, they made campaigns to help people switch into cheaper energy sources. These forms of communications have helped ease the tension from the people and create an opportunity for both the government and the people to work together.

Targeted Cash Transfers

Another form of subsidy delivery is through targeted cash transfers. The government should improve the mechanism of identifying the underserved and ensuring they receive the subsidies. They need to use at least 50 % of the savings in cash transfer mechanisms to mitigate the negative impacts on the underserved. Targeted cash transfers need to ensure that the laws are eligibility criteria are fair and will reach those who most need. Working the government or receiving pensions are not very fair eligibility criteria because the underserved most probably will not be working in the government and therefore will not be receiving pensions.

Scope and Methodology

The objective of the study is to study the impact of the new subsidy reform on low-income households in Egypt. We give a background on the issue and how the problem was looked at and handled before. We then look at the proposed subsidy reforms and then analyze its impact on the underserved households in Egypt. Brazil, Yemen and Iran are then the references we use as case studies to understand further their experience and how they were able to apply the subsidy cuts and reforms in their countries.

The methodology used was based on secondary sources in previous studies and data from the World Bank reports and the Egyptian Center for Economic Studies and Other Organizations in the past 10 years. We also refer to critique and observations from economic experts and scholars from journal articles or media.

References

- Abaza, D (2013). Let them eat vegetables: Egypt's wheat farmers hit hard by diesel price hikes. *Ahram Online*. Published January 13, 2013. Accessed April 22, 2013. URL: <http://english.ahram.org.eg/News/69016.aspx>
- AboAlabass, B (2013). Egypt Eyes Rising Electricity Prices as Cure for Summer Power Cuts. *Ahram Online*. Published April 8, 2013. Accessed May 5, 2013. URL: <http://english.ahram.org.eg/News/68716.aspx>
- Alsherif, A. (2013). Egypt's soaring energy subsidy bill to exceed previous estimate. Reuters. Chicago
- Castel, V. (2012). *Reforming energy subsidies in Egypt*. African Development Bank Brief.
- Clements, B. (2013). Energy subsidy reform: lessons and implications. International Monetary Fund (IMF)
- Egypt's Morsi Cuts Energy Subsidies (2012). Nuquday http://english.nuqudy.com/North_Africa/Egypt%E2%80%99s_Morsi_Cuts_-2840
- Egypt to abolish fuel subsidies as early as 2016: minister (2013). Alarabiya [.http://english.alarabiya.net/en/business/economy/2013/04/08/Egypt-to-abolish-fuel-subsidies-as-early-as-2016-minister.html](http://english.alarabiya.net/en/business/economy/2013/04/08/Egypt-to-abolish-fuel-subsidies-as-early-as-2016-minister.html)
- Elshahed, M. 2013. Upgrading Urban Egypt. *The Cairo Review of Global Affairs*. American University in Cairo. Published March 9, 2013. URL: <http://www.aucegypt.edu/gapp/cairoreview/pages/articleDetails.aspx?aid=312>
- Energy Ministers propose subsidy changes (2012). Nuqudy Newsletter. http://english.nuqudy.com/North_Africa/Egypt_Ministers_Pro-3342
- Fattouh B., El-Katiri L (2012), Energy subsidies in the Middle East and North Africa, *Energy Strategy Reviews*. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2012.11.004>
- Goldthau A., Sovacool B., (2011). The Uniqueness of The Energy Security, Justice, and Governance Problem. *Energy Policy Journal*.

Granado F, Coady D, Gillingham R (2012). The Unequal Benefits of Fuel Subsidies: A Review of Evidence for Developing Countries. *World Development* Vol.40, No. 11, pp. 2234-2248. URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2012.05.005>

Hussien,M (2013). Egypt's govt proposes subsidies cuts, tax increases to slash deficit. Ahramonline.

<http://english.ahram.org.eg/NewsContent/3/12/65680/Business/Economy/Egypt-s-govt-proposes-subsidies-cuts,-tax-increases.aspx>

International Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD). 2010. *Lessons Learned from Brazil's Experience with Fossil-Fuel Subsidies and their Reform*. Retrieved from: http://www.iisd.org/pdf/2010/lessons_brazil_fuel_subsidies.pdf

International Monetary Fund (IMF). 2013. Case Studies on Energy Subsidy reforms: Lessons and Implications. Retrieved from: <http://www.imf.org/external/np/pp/eng/2013/012813a.pdf>

Khattab A., 2007. The Impact of reducing energy subsidies on energy intensive industries in Egypt. *Egyptian Center for Economic Studies*. Working Paper No. 124 May 2007.

Rohac, D. (2013). Fixing Egypt's Subsidy Nightmare.The National Interest.

<http://nationalinterest.org/commentary/fixing-egypts-subsidy-nightmare-8254?page=1>

Salah El Din, D (2013). Power Crisis Darkens Outlook for Egypt.*Financial Times Limited*. Published January 7, 2013.Accessed: May 5, 2013. URL: <http://www.ft.com/intl/cms/s/0/2bb3ba82-58d9-11e2-99e6-00144feab49a.html#axzz2ShfwG2ku>

Shalaby, E. (2010). *The impact of phasing out energy subsidies on developing countries "a case study on Egypt"*. Berlin Conference On the Human Dimensions of Global Environmental Change.

Suding, P. (2010). Struggling Between Resources-Based and Sustainable Development Schemes—An Analysis of Egypt's Recent Energy Policy.*Energy Policy Journal*.

Tashima, R (2012). Power Shortage.*Business Today Egypt*.Published February 14, 2012.Accessed: May 5, 2013. URL: <http://www.businesstodayegypt.com/index.php?url=news/display/article/artId:310/Power-Shortage/secId:5>

Tashima, R. (2013). Currency Crisis. Business Today. News in Focus
<http://www.businesstodayegypt.com/article/artId:568/Currency-Crisis/secId:3>

Treazono,E., Saleh,H. (2013). Currency crisis hits Egypt's Wheat
Supply.Financialtimes.Middle East & North Africa.<http://www.ft.com/intl/cms/s/0/828043ca-7608-11e2-8eb6-00144feabdc0.html>

UNDP (2012).Energy Subsidies in the Arab World.*Arab Human Development Report
Research Paper Series.*

United National Development Program (UNDP). 2012. *Energy Subsidies in the Arab World.*
Retrieved from:
<http://www.undp.org/content/dam/undp/library/Environment%20and%20Energy/UNDP-EE-AHDR-Energy-Subsidies-2012-Final.pdf>

Vagliasindi, M. 2012. Implementing Energy Subsidy Reforms: Evidence from Developing
Countries.Directions in Development. Washington, DC: World Bank.

Vagliasindi. M. 2012. Implementing Energy Subsidy Reforms An Overview of the Key
Issues. Retrieved from: [http://www-
wds.worldbank.org/servlet/WDSContentServer/WDSP/IB/2012/07/09/000158349_20120709115206/Rendered/PDF/WPS6122.pdf](http://www-wds.worldbank.org/servlet/WDSContentServer/WDSP/IB/2012/07/09/000158349_20120709115206/Rendered/PDF/WPS6122.pdf)

World Bank (2005), Egypt Towards a More Effective Social Policy: Subsidies and Social
Safety Net. *Social and Economic Development Group*, NO. 33550-EG